

White Paper ID Number W017

Title of White Paper Star Formation in the Galactic Ecosystem

ID of Associated Expression of Interest E024

Topic Area of White Paper science programs, science topics and science themes

Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

Over the next decade, the Canadian community will play a leading role in answering key questions about the interaction between star formation and galaxy evolution. These opportunities flow from a productive decade since LRP 2010 that has yielded new insights into the connections between how stars form and their local galactic environment. All these past and future advances have capitalized upon a broad suite of instrumental access from the long-wavelength radio to the ultraviolet.

Galaxy evolution and star formation have traditionally been distinct subfields within astronomy, but the work since LRP 2010 has shown that the two are intimately connected. The buildup of the star forming main sequence and quenching of galaxies are both driven by star formation. Reciprocally, studies have also revealed that a galaxy's mass and morphology regulate the efficiency of ongoing star formation within it. These variations in efficiency are only now being clearly linked to changes in the properties of the star forming molecular medium and the conditions in the galactic interstellar medium. Over the next ten years, we will make a physically motivated connection between star formation and the broader galactic environment. This work focuses around five key questions and the survey-driven approaches that will enable Canadian researchers to come to clear answers over the next decade:

(1) How are ISM conditions and individual star formation events influenced by the galactic environment? We are carrying out the surveys of galaxy populations needed to make a census of ISM conditions across a statistically significant number of galaxies. These focus on careful work in the Milky Way and nearby galaxies where individual star formation events can be discerned.

What processes regulate the formation of the molecular ISM and its organization into massive structures? Surveying a broad range of galactic environments is also a key data set for addressing this question, but this must also be done using new tracers to access obscured physics. Specifically, we will need good access to the submillimetre so we can execute high quality polarization measurements for studying the magnetic field and fine structure lines ([C I], [O I], [C II]) to trace the material being channeled into star forming clouds.

What processes disrupt the neutral ISM leading to the quenching of galaxies? We will make surveys of Galactic and extragalactic star forming regions across the wavebands to calibrate how stars inject momentum and energy into their host galaxy ISM. We will establish how this feedback depends on local star formation properties, including the including cluster mass function.

How does local star formation relate to the different mode of star formation seen in $z > 2$ Universe? Studies of lensed systems, notably with ALMA, allow for resolved studies of a different mode of star formation in galactic assembly. However, these studies rely on tracers that are difficult to observe without new access to the submillimetre and far infrared. Through local mapping of the tracers typically used in high redshift studies, we can resolve how these tracers are influenced by local conditions, providing a better calibration of the properties in distant systems.

How does the galactic environment predict other aspects of the star formation process beyond the star formation rate? Multiwaveband surveys will also extend our studies beyond simply answering how the star formation rate changes, turning to questions of variations in the initial mass function, the

initial cluster mass function, and binary property distributions.

To address these central questions in the next decade requires that we maintain and expand our access to a broad suite of observational facilities. In particular, we must remain actively engaged with ALMA, which is still in its early stages of discovery. We must also continue strong investment in high-performance computing necessary to carry out the expensive, multi-physics simulations of star formation in a galactic context. We continue to require access to single-dish radio to submillimetre facilities such as CCAT-p, the JCMT, and the GBT, and the DRAO Synthesis Telescope to carry out wide area mapping of our own Galaxy. ALMA should not be regarded as a replacement for this class of observatory. Finally, participating in next generation radio interferometers, namely the SKA and ngVLA, are needed to carry out resolved surveys of star formation and the interstellar medium beyond the nearest galaxies.

Lead author and affiliation Erik Rosolowsky (U. Alberta)

Email address of lead author rosolowsky@ualberta.ca

Other authors and affiliations

Laurent Drissen (U. Laval)
Laura Fissel (Queen's)
Alex Hill (UBC)
Doug Johnstone (NRC)
Gilles Joncas (U. Laval)
Eric Koch (U. Alberta)
Chris Matzner (U. Toronto)
Rene Plume (U. Calgary)
Sarah Sadavoy (Queen's)
Mehrnoosh Tahani (U. Calgary)
Christine Wilson (McMaster)

1 Introduction: Star Formation Drives Galaxy Evolution

Galaxy evolution is driven by mergers and accretion, feedback from active galactic nuclei (AGN), and star formation. This white paper focuses on how star formation shapes galaxy evolution and how the broader galactic environment regulates the star formation process.

1.1 Overview

Star formation is characterized by a rapid cycling of matter from the interstellar medium into a new generation of stars. Stars form in molecular clouds and high mass stars give off sufficient ionizing radiation and stellar winds (broadly called “feedback”) to disrupt the natal molecular clouds and inject energy and momentum into the ISM around the star formation event. We are keenly interested in how the host galaxy environment influences the efficiency and timescales of the star formation process and the reciprocal influence of star formation on how the galaxy evolves. There is substantial evidence, most of it discovered since LRP2010, that the interstellar medium and the star formation process change systematically as a function of galactic environment.

In the solar neighbourhood, stars form in distinct molecular clouds, but a cloud-based description of the molecular medium is not universally applicable. In regions like the central molecular zone (CMZ) of our galaxy or the star forming regions that light up ultraluminous infrared galaxies (ULIRGs), the clouds blend into a single massive gas structure. Within these large molecular zones, the stars will form in the relatively dense subregions.

Understanding star formation in the galactic ecosystem requires synthesizing three separate perspectives informed by the different physical scales studied: (1) studies of individual star forming regions, (2) studies of the ISM and unresolved star formation in nearby galaxies, and (3) surveys of many galaxies to understand galaxy evolution. These three separate intellectual threads must be woven together for a robust understanding of galaxy evolution.

Star formation itself proceeds on scales < 0.1 pc as star forming cores collapse to form single stellar systems. The scales are best studied in the Milky Way, focusing primarily on the solar neighbourhood where the proximity allows high linear resolution observations. Studies of these star forming events, in the context of the molecular clouds in which they are formed are the subject of whitepaper E025 by di Francesco et al. The star formation process establishes the initial mass function of stars (IMF) but also the initial distribution of binary properties, and the organization of newly formed stars into clusters through the initial cluster mass function (ICMF).

For nearby galaxies ($d < 100$ Mpc), the galactic context of star formation is explored through studies of the star formation law which considers how the reservoir of (molecular) gas is converted into stars as a function of the environment in the host galaxy. This perspective requires UV to near IR observations to determine star formation rate but also long-wavelength observations to measure the mass of the gas in the ISM. The fundamental work on the star formation law was presented by Kennicutt (1998) who found that the surface density of star formation (Σ_{SFR} , with units of mass formed per area per time), averaged over galaxy disks, scaled with the surface density of neutral gas (Σ_{gas}): $\Sigma_{\text{SFR}} \propto \Sigma_{\text{gas}}^{1.4}$. The relationship spanned ordinary disk galaxies like the Milky Way up to ULIRGs.

The final perspective on star formation in the context of galaxies was driven by large optical surveys of galaxies, notably the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS). These SDSS observations focused on the relationship between star formation, the stellar content in galaxies, and the role of Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN) since all could be addressed through wide-area optical surveys. From the huge numbers of galaxies observed the SDSS, galaxy-scale star formation came to be defined around the star forming main sequence of galaxies (Brinchmann et al., 2004; Noeske et al., 2007). Elliptical and lenticular galaxies formed the majority of *quenched* systems, falling off the main sequence, showing no cold ISM or ongoing star formation. The process of quenching remains actively studied including the role of feedback from star formation or AGN at removing or disrupting the neutral ISM.

1.2 Scientific Developments Since LRP2010

Over the past 10 years, we have made several new discoveries that have refined our understanding of star formation in the galactic context. We present the major advances in the field, highlighting work with Canadian contributions in specific areas with **red** text.

Figure 1: The Star Formation Law as presented in Leroy et al. (2013) using the HERACLES survey of 30 nearby disk galaxies. Each datum represents the SFR and molecular gas surface density measured on 1 kpc scales, with the red points indicating average values within bins. The diagonal dotted lines show $\log_{10}(t_{\text{dep}}/\text{yr})$. Molecular gas surface densities are estimated from CO(2-1) observations and the star formation rate is determined from broadband infrared+ultraviolet observations. Assuming a fixed conversion factor between CO line intensity and molecular gas mass yields $\Sigma_{\text{SFR}} \propto \Sigma_{\text{mol}}$. The star formation rate is independent of atomic gas surface density (Σ_{atomic}). This figure shows that, on 1-kpc scales within nearby galaxies, the efficiency of star formation is roughly constant.

Figure 2: Galaxy-integrated molecular gas depletion time as a function of stellar mass for 191 galaxies drawn from the xCOLD GASS sample of Saintonge et al. (2017). Molecular gas masses are measured from CO(2-1) emission with a metallicity-dependent conversion factor. Stellar masses and star formation rates are measured from SDSS spectroscopy or broad band imaging in the ultraviolet and infrared. The red line shows the median depletion time in bins of stellar mass. This figure shows that the efficiency of star formation depends significantly on the stellar mass of the host galaxy.

On kpc scales in nearby galaxies, the star formation law depends linearly on molecular gas content. Surveys of atomic and molecular gas in nearby galaxies showed that, for a given kpc-scale region, the star formation rate depends linearly on the molecular gas content (Figure 1; Leroy et al., 2013). This measurement is frequently recast as there being a roughly constant depletion time $t_{\text{dep}} \equiv \Sigma_{\text{mol}}/\Sigma_{\text{SFR}} \sim 2 \text{ Gyr}$, which serves as a first-order parameterization of the efficiency of star formation, characterizing the star forming galaxy population with $M_{\star} \sim 10^{11} M_{\odot}$.

There is significant variation in the depletion time that changes from galaxy to galaxy. A linear star formation law emerges is discernible only by considering a relatively narrow range of galaxy properties. There is substantial variation in the depletion time when a wide range of galaxies is considered. The main sequence of galaxy evolution emerged as a key description of the overall galaxy population, forming a well defined locus in specific star formation rate ($\text{sSFR} \equiv \text{SFR}/M_{\star}$) vs stellar mass space M_{\star} . Overall, more massive galaxies have lower sSFR but they also show longer depletion times, indicating that star formation is systematically less efficient in more massive galaxies (Figure 2; Saintonge et al., 2017). Probing this behaviour is essential for understanding the quenching of galaxies. Studies also show that the cluster environment can suppress the efficiency of star formation (Mok et al., 2017).

Depletion time decreases systematically in several types of galaxy. Starburst galaxies, ULIRGs, and mergers all show significantly more efficient star formation (e.g., the JCMT survey work in Wilson et al., 2012). The depletion time also decreases for high redshift systems, indicating that star formation process was fundamentally more efficient when the star formation rate of the universe was at a maximum at $z \approx 2$ (Tacconi et al., 2018).

Star formation occurs in dense gas, but the star formation efficiency of dense gas also varies. Most studies of the molecular medium in galaxies focus on using CO emission as a proxy for molecular gas since it is readily excited to emit in nearly all gas conditions. Molecules like HCN, with a large electric dipole, emit more efficiently in the dense gas where stars form inside molecular clouds. Early work by Gao & Solomon (2004) argued that the dense gas star formation efficiency was constant from the solar neighbourhood to ULIRGs. However, studies of the CMZ (Kauffmann et al., 2017) and nearby disk galaxies (Usero et al., 2015) showed that even the dense gas star formation efficiency varies significantly with galactic environment.

Theoretical work argues for the star formation efficiency per free fall time as the central parameter a holistic view of the star formation process. Several theoretical and numerical studies (Federrath & Klessen, 2012, and references therein) have argued that the parameter $\epsilon_{\text{ff}} \equiv \dot{M}_{\star} t_{\text{ff}} / M_{\text{mol}}$ represents the key microphysics of the star formation process. This ratio compares the actual rate of star formation (\dot{M}_{\star}) to the maximally efficient star formation rate where all gas collapses to form stars on a free-fall time ($M_{\text{mol}}/t_{\text{ff}}$). Some theoretical work argues that magnetic fields and turbulence set ϵ_{ff} to be constant across galaxies, there is observational evidence that the parameter varies in cluster forming regions (Murray, 2011; Lee et al., 2016) or depending on galactic environment (Utomo et al., 2018; Wilson et al., 2019).

The magnetic field remains a poorly understood component of the galactic environment, but its effects cannot be neglected in the diffuse ISM. Surveys of field strength and geometry reach the conclusion that the molecular medium is supercritical, so that the effects of the magnetic field are not strong enough halt gravitational collapse in clouds (Crutcher, 2012). However, the same work shows that the atomic medium is subcritical so that magnetic forces cannot be neglected. Understanding the morphology and strength of magnetic fields both in the galactic scales and smaller is particularly important for understanding how the molecular medium forms and fragments into massive structures. Canadian researchers have made significant contributions in understanding the Galactic magnetic fields and the magnetic fields of local star forming regions. Recently, Tahani et al. (2018) proposed and demonstrated a new method based on Faraday rotation to detect the line of sight component of magnetic fields associated with giant molecular clouds (scales of 10-90 pc) in the Galaxy. This method used an already published observational catalog (Taylor et al., 2009), however, more precise results spanning more regions will be done with different facilities such as the Synthesis Telescope at the Dominion Radio Astrophysical Observatory.

2 Facilities

2.1 Observational Practicalities

Studying star formation in the galactic context relies on tracers of emission, necessitating broad access to a variety of telescope facilities. Because of dust extinction and radiative reprocessing, we cannot use optical telescopes to observe stars forming directly. The hydrogen in atomic and molecular gas does not emit significantly in the optical or UV. Instead we rely on long-wavelength observations to avoid dust extinction and tracer species to infer the gas content. The key wavebands for these studies are:

- Decimetre-wavelength radio facilities which observe the 21-cm line from HI, nonthermal radiation from the magnetoionic medium, supernova remnants and active galactic nuclei, as well as thermal continuum and radio recombination lines from ionized gas. The key facilities used by the Canadian community for these observations are the DRAO Synthesis Telescope, the Karl G. Jansky Very Large Array (VLA), the Robert C. Byrd Green Bank Telescope (GBT). The Square Kilometre Array (SKA) precursors are starting to contribute in this domain as well (ASKAP, MeerKAT; see report from AACS for details).
- Millimetre- and centimetre-wavelength observations detect the rotational and vibrational transitions of molecules, notably CO, the brightest tracer of the star forming molecular medium. The Atacama Large Millime-

tre/submillimetre Array (ALMA) is the main Canadian facility making these observations but Open Skies access to the GBT and VLA are essential facilities for Canadian success.

- The submillimetre waveband and far infrared wavebands ($\nu \gtrsim 300$ GHz) observe the higher energy transitions of molecules in the ISM. However, this waveband also observes the thermal continuum emission of dust grains and key cooling lines of the ISM (the fine structure lines of [OI], [CI], [CII]). Since dust is well mixed through the neutral ISM, its thermal emission provides a good tracer of gas column density. Dust grains are aspherical and align with the magnetic field, so their emission is polarized and indicates the field direction and strength. ALMA is the main facility operating in this waveband now, but the early part of the decade saw major progress from a Canadian stake in the James Clerk Maxwell Telescope (JCMT) and the *Herschel* Space Observatory.
- The mid- and near-infrared wavebands provide good tracers of the warm ISM near star forming regions through the emission from polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). The near-IR also provides a minimal extinction view of the stellar structure in galaxies, by observing the thermal emission from stellar photospheres with only minimal absorption from dust. Though there was no official Canadian participation, the Wide-field Infrared Survey Explorer (WISE) and warm phase mission of the *Spitzer* Space Telescope (SST) were the key facilities operating in these bands.
- The optical waveband is the primary waveband for tracing the stellar populations in our Galaxy and others. Broad-band photometry from the space and ground provide wide-area mapping of stellar populations, inferring current star formation and the star formation history. $H\alpha$ emission provides the best tracer of the ionization from young, massive stars. The key Canadian facility here is the Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope (CFHT) which provides high quality, wide area imaging through MegaCam as well as integral field spectroscopy ($11' \times 11'$, $0.3''$ pixels, $R = 10 - 10000$) with the imaging FTS SITELLE (Drissen et al., 2019). Optical Integral Field Unit (IFU) spectroscopy has provided new insights through SDSS-IV (MANGA) and the *Hubble* Space Telescope (HST) remains the premier observatory for high resolution optical imaging of galaxies.
- The near ultraviolet is particularly important for observations of star formation in galaxies since the photospheric emission of high-mass stars stands out in this waveband. HST provides observational capability in the near ultraviolet but the Canadian-built Ultraviolet Imaging Telescope (UVIT) on the AstroSat mission is the best available imager in the far ultraviolet waveband.

Observations in both the Milky Way and external galaxies are essential for progress. Because of proximity, studies of star formation in the Milky Way provide the best available insight on how individual star formation events interact with the local ISM. These studies suffer from heavy dust extinction in the Galactic plane, limiting optical and infrared studies. In nearby galaxies, individual stars unresolved or marginally resolved, but the connection between the galactic environment and these stars is clearer just from the “top-down” view of the system. Finally, more distant galaxies are essential for understanding the star formation properties of large populations of galaxies.

2.2 Theoretical Practicalities

While “pencil-and-paper” theoretical studies are important in understanding star formation in the galactic context, numerical simulation is at the heart of this field. Star formation is a multi-physics process, with interactions between turbulence, magnetic fields, gravitation, radiation, and chemistry. Understanding the interaction between some of these effects requires expensive numerical simulations, and only a few groups globally attempt to include many of these effects, exploring the star formation process within a galactic context (e.g. Benincasa et al., 2016). Instead, most simulations of galaxies treat star formation as “subgrid physics,” with simple models based on the star formation laws like that of Kennicutt (1998). State of the art numerical simulations of these multiphysics processes invariably require high-performance computing resources, provided domestically by Compute Canada and the regional computing consortia (e.g., WestGrid, SHARCnet, Calcul Quebec).

2.3 Key Facility Changes Since LRP2010

Canadian access to several facilities played key roles for making progress in this field over the past decade. These facilities are summarized below, identifying major projects with those facilities that feature heavy participation by Canadian scientists.

ALMA: The most significant change in facilities has been the early science operations of ALMA. From the first observations in 2011, ALMA has reshaped the study of star formation in galaxies, by making orders-of-magnitude improvements in (sub)millimetre observations. Canadians have participated broadly in ALMA, with Canadian scientists participating in $\sim 20\%$ of ALMA projects (G. Schieven, private communication). The earliest cycles of ALMA observations focused on single-target studies, but as the observatory's efficiency has increased, the Canadian community has been able to lead Large Programs with a focus on star formation in the galactic ecosystem (e.g., PHANGS and VERTICO studying nearby galaxies).

JCMT: Canada officially transitioned out from the JCMT partnership in 2014, but the Canadian university community has remained successful at securing funding from universities as well as occasional national funding bodies, including a one-time grant through NSERC-RTI. The JCMT began observing Large Programs in the early part of the decade. The Canadian community has been active before and after the change in composition for the JCMT partnership, including leadership in the several relevant surveys, notably the JPS and CHIMPS2 surveys (surveying the Galactic plane and central molecular zone) and NGLS, JINGLE, and MALATANG (surveying nearby galaxies).

Herschel: National participation in the *Herschel* mission, including the construction of one of the main detectors, allowed many members of the Canadian community to participate several of the main consortia including KINGFISH (nearby galaxies), HERM33ES (Survey of M33), HOBYS (high mass star formation in the Milky Way) and the Gould Belt Survey (GBS). Since the *Herschel* mission required cryogenically cooled detectors, it was a limited mission lifetime.

JVLA: The Very Large Array completed its major upgrade at the beginning of the decade, with the Canadian-built WIDAR correlator being a cornerstone of the enhanced capabilities at the observatory. The improvements allowed for order-of-magnitude improvements in the continuum sensitivity, which enabled high-efficiency surveys of nearby galaxies and the Galactic plane (e.g., the THOR survey of the Galactic plane or the CHANG-ES survey of galaxy halos). The Canadian community made frequent use of the JVLA through the North American Partnership for Radio Astronomy (NAPRA) which expired in 2017, and using the Open Skies access policy of the NSF since that point.

Compute Canada: As part of its support for high-performance computing in Canada, the Canada Foundation for Innovation (CFI) required the establishment of Compute Canada as an umbrella national organization spanning the different regional computing consortia that existed before that time. The new organization has overseen the deployment of several new high performance computing facilities including systems optimized for the numerical simulations required to study galaxy-scale star formation (*niagara* at U. Toronto), and capability clusters that show good performance on large data processing (*cedar* at SFU). However, future improvements on resource allocation policies in compute Canada could help the speed of both theoretical and observational research. Currently, the resource (time and storage) allocation competitions are held annually and postdoctoral fellows are not eligible to apply for allocations. Giving postdoctoral fellows the opportunity to apply directly will help the speed of research in this field.

3 Key Progress for the Next Decade

3.1 Driving Science Questions

Over the next decade, we are poised to answer several key questions that will allow us to understand the link between star formation and galaxy evolution.

- **How are ISM conditions and individual star formation events influenced by the galactic environment?**
The Milky Way provides an unequalled perspective on individual star forming regions. However, our per-

Figure 3: NGC 6300 in CO(2-1) emission as observed by ALMA (top) and HST (bottom) on a common image scale. The figure illustrates the dramatic improvement in imaging quality achieved by ALMA compared to previous generations of interferometers. ALMA efficiently provides arcsecond-scale imaging of galaxies which enables comparison with optical tracers for understanding star formation in the context of galaxies.

spective from within the disk of the Galaxy makes it difficult to connect our detailed understanding to the broader galactic environment. A better understanding of galaxy structure will be driven by a wealth of Milky Way focused surveys, notably the Gaia mission and the Local Volume Mapper as part of SDSS-V. With these new surveys, we will be able to understand how, exactly, galactic environment affects individual star forming events, with a focus on the CMZ, the bar regions, and the outer disk of the galaxy.

- **What processes regulate the formation of the molecular ISM and its organization into massive structures?** Star formation studies have focused on the molecular medium, but the precursor material for molecular cloud formation is atomic and ionized. The flow of material through the cosmic web and into the centres of galaxies is best traced through atomic gas observations. Understanding how atomic gas is channeled into galaxies and the physics for assembling molecular clouds (gravitation, magnetic fields, galactic dynamics) will be far better understood through the increased resolution of GHz interferometers, namely the ngVLA, and SKA and its precursor facilities. Instrumental advances in measuring the polarization of dust emission (ALMA, JCMT, CCAT-prime, BLAST-TNG) and spectral lines (ALMA, DRAO’s Galt Telescope) will finally establish the influence of the magnetic field in regulating the assembly of star forming clouds.
- **What processes disrupt the neutral ISM leading the quenching of galaxies?** While observational work finds real variation in the star formation efficiency of molecular gas, we do not understand how this changing efficiency relates to the quenching seen in the galactic population as a whole. Feedback must play a role and specifically AGN activity remains poorly studied on the scales relevant to individual star formation events. The Canadian-led SIGNALS Large program at the CFHT (Rousseau-Nepton et al., 2019) will study a sample of 50,000 HII regions and diffuse ionized gas in nearby galaxies. These observations will directly trace photoionization feedback and its relationship to the molecular medium. Since the Milky Way is not currently hosting an AGN, we lack the detailed observational perspective on AGN feedback that we have on star formation feedback. However, through targeted observations of AGN combined with population studies, the next decade will establish the connection between the star formation process and quenching.
- **How does local star formation relate to the different mode of star formation seen in $z \geq 2$ Universe?** Observations of galaxies at high redshift, from “cosmic noon” at $z \sim 2$ where the cosmic star formation reaches a maximum to the earliest star forming systems at $z > 7$ rely on redshifted species such as [C II] and high- J CO lines that are difficult to observe at $z = 0$ (Carilli & Walter, 2013). These observations indicate that the star formation that governed galaxy assembly operated in a clumpy chaotic model compared to the disk-regulated star formation we see locally. Improvements in instrumentation will allow the study of these

tracers locally and expand the study of resolved molecular gas in distant systems enabled by gravitational lensing.

- **How does the galactic environment predict other aspects of the star formation process beyond the star formation rate?** Finally, the star formation process on the galactic scale typically focuses only on the star formation rate. However, the star formation process must also determine the initial mass function, the initial cluster mass function, the fraction of stars organized into bound clusters, and the distributions of binary/multiple system parameters. The degree to which the host galaxy sets any of these parameters is unknown and any significant variation will have an influence on galaxy evolution but also on our interpretation of transient populations (e.g., gravitational wave events), the population of planetary systems, and the search for life.

3.2 New and Improved Tracers

In the next decade, improved instrumentation and ongoing use of existing facilities will allow the community to use new tracers and observational techniques to answer the driving questions.

Wide-area, spectrally-resolved observatories in the submillimetre and far infrared will dramatically expand local ($z \sim 0$) observations of the [C_I] fine structure lines and high- J CO rotational transitions. These lines are the main tracers for high redshift observations of the molecular ISM. There are several lines of development for high-altitude submillimetre observatories (CCAT-p) which are needed for wide area mapping of these tracers, providing a local benchmark to the high- z studies and detailed understanding of how these tracers relate to star formation. The [C_{II}] lines at 1.9 THz are also used for high- z work but these will continue to require flying or space-based observatories such as SOFIA or SPICA.

These same submillimetre facilities also focus on polarization capabilities, which will see improved mapping of the magnetic field as inferred from dust polarization. Pushing to higher resolution and deeper sensitivity will improve maps of the magnetic field in nearby galaxies. The role of the large scale galactic magnetic field is unexplored in most studies of galaxy-scale star formation.

Finally, the high spatial resolution of near- and mid-infrared enabled by the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) will resolve the earliest stages of star and cluster formation in nearby galaxies. This new perspective are essential to address questions about variations of the IMF, ICMF, and binary populations.

3.3 Key Facilities

Advances in our key science questions require access to a wide range of facilities, spanning multiple wavebands.

- ALMA remains a critical facility still in its early phases of science with substantial expansions of its capabilities planned between now and 2030 (see E004). Maintaining access to this facility is the top priority for continued progress in this science area.
- Expansion of High Performance Computing facilities under Compute Canada and its successor organization is needed to return to Canadians being able to execute field-leading research in this area. Even with the recent refresh of facilities, support levels are well below comparable countries.
- Continued access to Single Dish Submillimetre Facilities remains an essential complement to ALMA access. CCAT-p operates at higher frequencies than other submillimetre facilities with a high-performance spectrometer (CHAI) that will efficiently map galaxies. The new capabilities will provide new access to previously hard-to-study tracers (the magnetic field, warm CO and [C_I]). The balloon-borne polarimeter BLAST-TNG will map magnetic fields in both nearby galaxies and local molecular clouds. The Canadian community remains closely engaged with the JCMT through new instrumental initiatives and the large survey programs that lay the groundwork for ALMA follow-up.

- Participation in both the SKA and ngVLA would benefit this science cluster, though the ngVLA is more immediately relevant to the star forming ISM. In addition to molecular line tracers, the ngVLA observations of the 10-40 GHz thermal continuum and radio recombination lines provide some of the best available diagnostics of embedded high mass star formation. Both facilities will provide $\sim 1''$ high-fidelity mapping of the 21-cm HI line, dramatically increasing the sample of galaxies where HI can be traced on giant molecular clouds scales, critical for understanding how molecular clouds form across different galactic environments.
- Though Canadian participation in SDSS-V is minimal, the new Local Volume Mapper instrument will use optical emission lines to measure conditions in the ionized ISM throughout the Milky Way and nearby systems. This science area would directly benefit from any large scale participation in SDSS-V.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

The past decade of research has illustrated that star formation both shapes galaxy evolution and is controlled by the local galactic environment. The fields of galaxy evolution and local star formation are converging, leading to several questions that stand poised to answer from 2020-2030:

- How are ISM conditions and individual star formation events influenced by the galactic environment?
- What processes regulate the formation of the molecular ISM and its organization into massive structures?
- What processes disrupt the neutral ISM leading to the quenching of galaxies?
- How does local star formation relate to the different mode of star formation seen in $z \geq 2$ Universe?
- How does the galactic environment predict other aspects of the star formation process beyond the star formation rate?

These questions are turning out to be at the heart of the study galaxy evolution. Their answers are required for a robust understanding of the star forming main sequence of galaxies, and more broadly, our own origins and the galactic environment in which we live.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

With the basic measurements of the contributing fields well established, the scientific risks are relatively low. Correctly resolving systematic effects will clear a major hurdle in advancing our understanding. Most ISM studies rely on tracers, for example CO emission as a proxy for molecular gas. Careful studies are needed to understand the correct way to interpret the tracer as a proxy for the more massive but invisible material it represents. Our interpretations will remain shaky unless we have the facility access and numerical simulations required to carry out these important calibration studies.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Over the next decade, Canadian leadership in the study of galaxy-scale star formation will flow from two key areas of strength. First, expertise in long-wavelength instrumentation from the radio to the submillimetre (NRC and the university community) will allow participation in the next-generation facilities that are required to answer our pressing questions. In particular, access to improved observational modes will allow us study new tracers such as submillimetre lines and dust polarization. This expertise has led to continued leadership in the JCMT operations, being founding members of the CCAT-p collaboration, and playing leadership roles in the SPICA mission.

Second, the Canadian community has a demonstrated history of developing and leading the large surveys that will be needed to uniformly study the wide range of galactic environments needed to make progress. This strength is backed by a robust data management infrastructure built around the Canadian Astronomy Data Centre.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

The Canadian community participates broadly in the study of star formation and the galaxy evolution. Several major surveys that directly support this effort have been led from Canada starting with the Canadian Galactic Plane Survey in the 2000s and including surveys in the past decade on the JCMT (NGLS, JPS, JINGLE, CHIMPS2), ALMA (PHANGS, VERTICO), *Herschel* (HOBYS, GBS, HiGal), and the JVLA (CHANG-ES).

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

Leadership in this scientific area will continue Canadian participation in flagship facilities such as ALMA. This work will also position our community and critically our HQP trainees to use the next generation of astronomical facilities, notably the SKA, ngVLA, and SPICA, all of which will have the main phase of their operations in 2030.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

Making the concrete links between star formation and the galactic ecosystem builds on a generation of investment by the community in building up expertise in the long-wavelength observations that are central to our goals.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

The primary risk is access to best-available facilities, notably facilities across different wavebands, with a focus on the radio to the far infrared. Much of the key science proposed here requires wide-area mapping with good spatial dynamic range. In the submillimetre and millimetre wavebands, this means continued access to single dish facilities. While ALMA is a field-leading instrument, it is not efficient at wide area mapping, requiring access to facilities like the JCMT, CCAT-p, and the GBT.

The pending reorganization of national high-performance computing (HPC) facilities could represent another risk to this science track. If the new national digital resource manager prioritizes research investment and access to facilities, this field will benefit from increased simulation capacity. However, without an ongoing commitment to growth of these resources, we will not be able to contribute effectively through simulations.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

As a research umbrella, the primary benefits for Canadians come from education and outreach opportunities, as well as through HQP training. In particular, the panchromatic and statistical nature of this science area necessitates that HQP develop a suite of skills that is transferable to industry, notably careers in instrument

building, data science and image processing. These same challenges also offer interdisciplinary research opportunities, notably making connections with computer scientists and statisticians.

References

Benincasa, S. M., Wadsley, J., Couchman, H. M. P., & Keller, B. W. 2016, *MNRAS*, 462, 3053

Brinchmann, J., Charlot, S., White, S. D. M., et al. 2004, *MNRAS*, 351, 1151

Carilli, C. L., & Walter, F. 2013, *ARA&A*, 51, 105

Crutcher, R. M. 2012, *ARA&A*, 50, 29

Drissen, L., Martin, T., Rousseau-Nepton, L., et al. 2019, *MNRAS*, 485, 3930

Federrath, C., & Klessen, R. S. 2012, *ApJ*, 761, 156

Gao, Y., & Solomon, P. M. 2004, *ApJ*, 606, 271

Kauffmann, J., Pillai, T., Zhang, Q., et al. 2017, *A&A*, 603, A89

Kennicutt, Robert C., J. 1998, *ApJ*, 498, 541

Lee, E. J., Miville-Deschênes, M.-A., & Murray, N. W. 2016, *ApJ*, 833, 229

Leroy, A. K., Walter, F., Sandstrom, K., et al. 2013, *AJ*, 146, 19

Mok, A., Wilson, C. D., Knapen, J. H., et al. 2017, *MNRAS*, 467, 4282

Murray, N. 2011, *ApJ*, 729, 133

Noeske, K. G., Weiner, B. J., Faber, S. M., et al. 2007, *ApJ*, 660, L43

Rousseau-Nepton, L., Martin, R. P., Robert, C., et al. 2019, *MNRAS*, 489, 5530

Saintonge, A., Catinella, B., Tacconi, L. J., et al. 2017, *ApJS*, 233, 22

Tacconi, L. J., Genzel, R., Saintonge, A., et al. 2018, *ApJ*, 853, 179

Tahani, M., Plume, R., Brown, J. C., & Kainulainen, J. 2018, *A&A*, 614, A100

Taylor, A. R., Stil, J. M., & Sunstrum, C. 2009, *ApJ*, 702, 1230

Usero, A., Leroy, A. K., Walter, F., et al. 2015, *AJ*, 150, 115

Utomo, D., Sun, J., Leroy, A. K., et al. 2018, *ApJ*, 861, L18

Wilson, C. D., Elmegreen, B. G., Bemis, A., & Brunetti, N. 2019, *ApJ*, 882, 5

Wilson, C. D., Warren, B. E., Israel, F. P., et al. 2012, *MNRAS*, 424, 3050